

A NEW INEQUALITY FOR THE SMARANDACHE FUNCTION

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Theorem. Let $S(m) = \min\{k \in \mathbb{N} : m \mid k!\}$ be the Smarandache Function, and $a_k, b_k \in \mathbb{N}^*$ ($k=1,2,\dots,n$), then we have the following inequality

$$S\left(\prod_{k=1}^n (a_k!)^{b_k}\right) \leq \sum_{k=1}^n a_k b_k$$

Proof:

$$\frac{\sum_{k=1}^n (a_k b_k)!}{\prod_{k=1}^n (a_k!)^{b_k}} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n (a_k b_k)!}{\prod_{k=1}^n (a_k b_k)!} * \frac{\prod_{k=1}^n (a_k b_k)!}{\prod_{k=1}^n (a_k!)^{b_k}} =$$

$$\binom{a_1 b_1 + a_2 b_2 + \dots + a_m b_m}{a_1 b_1} \binom{a_2 b_2 + \dots + a_m b_m}{a_2 b_2} \dots \binom{a_{m-1} b_{m-1} + a_m b_m}{a_{m-1} b_{m-1}}$$

$$\left(\prod_{k=1}^n \binom{a_k b_k}{a_k} \dots \binom{3a_k}{a_k} \binom{2a_k}{a_k} \right) \in \mathbb{N}^*$$

From this result

$$S\left(\prod_{k=1}^n (a_k!)^{b_k}\right) \leq \sum_{k=1}^n a_k b_k$$